

University of Helsinki
Subject Teacher Education Programme

Oral Assessment in Mathematics: A Pedagogical Exploration in Finnish Secondary Schools

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1. Introduction

1.1 Oral Assessment

Oral assessment can be defined as assessing students by questioning them rather than administering a paper-based test. The process is such that teachers do not have a ready-made question, but the discussion can develop so that the teacher can measure the student's understanding of the concepts and give supportive feedback to help the student get to the desired level of knowledge. This style of assessment is being used as a means of summative assessment in universities around the world but this research aims to encourage more use of this assessment style as a means of formative assessment at the high school level so that students can be motivated both internally and externally to succeed during their studies.

The processes involved in this assessment style were given by Broadfoot et al. (2002) which are diagnosing the current level of the student's knowledge, setting a desired level that the student should be, and determining what measure of work to be done to get to the desired level. Also, this form of assessment provides options for students who have writing and examination anxiety. But like any other forms of assessment, it comes with its limitations and the next section will discuss the limitations and possible solutions to these limitations.

1.2 Limitations of oral assessment

This research has assisted the writer in finding at least 4 limitations to oral assessment in mathematics and by extension to oral assessment in other subjects taught at the high school level (Lukio). Since the research was conducted at only 3 schools due to logistics reasons, we hope that further research with more schools as part of the data collection process would yield more possible limitations and their solutions. The first two are the major problems while the other 2 usually not so uncommon. The limitations are:

1.2.1 Time

This is the most significant of the limitations, since the teaching profession is already a time-demanding job and teachers rarely have time for other time outside teaching and other school businesses, it might seem unrealistic to discuss having an oral assessment with each student. The solution to this limitation lies within the school classrooms. In the 3 schools, classroom seating arrangements are usually in groups of 4, where students work together as a group or as individuals when required.

So rather than orally assessing each student, it will save time if teachers can formatively assess students in groups of 3 or 4. It is also possible that a teacher switches the student groups when the assessment is done so that the true level of understanding can be assessed. The issue of determining a student's true level and helping the students to understand their true potential is what leads to the second limitation of this assessment.

1.2.2 Over-grading and Under-grading

With regards to formative oral assessment, it is important that a teacher helps students to know their true level, understand what to do to move to the desired level, and help them to get there. But in most cases, students can either over-grade or under-grade themselves or their true level. At such times, it becomes the duty of the teacher to help readjust their view. The proposed solution to that is the Dunning-Kruger effect found in Dunning et al (2003). It is attached as an appendix to this report. Some students might have a high level of confidence but a low level of knowledge and as such find themselves on the peak of Mt. Stupid.

With effort, the teacher can help them to navigate safely through the program termination zone and valley of despair to get to the slope of enlightenment and at this point, steadiness is just the only thing needed for the student to reach the plateau of sustainability. Doing this takes time and effort from the teacher and the student and that is why the emphasis is on using formative oral assessment rather than summative.

1.2.3 Lack of student cooperation

Though this is rare, both students and teachers can be at a different level of learning. Since this stage is a very strong stage of students' lives where hormones are just developing and so many things are happening at once, lack of focus can cause the student not to cooperate with the plan and supportive feedback of the teacher. In this case, the teacher should try to discuss with the student and parent what is best for the student, and something a prep talk could be all it takes to get the student back on track.

1.2.4 Inadequate emotional support for teachers

Teachers give so much formative support to students during learning and as such it is important that they get some themselves too. But as in most cases, teachers are getting less emotional support these days and the meaning is that most teachers start to view support as something to do when things are going bad and not as what students need even when all seems well and okay. Teachers must pay attention to themselves by taking time to rest, doing what they love, and doing other things that help keep them in good mental and physical condition.

Next, we will talk about the types of classroom learning that support formative oral assessment in mathematics as was seen in the research.

1.3 Classroom learning that supports oral assessment

In recent times, there have been many questions asked about the generic way of teaching where teachers do all the talking and students do most of the writing. One such question is: Does this kind of teaching style support learning? It is important to know that to some extent, the answer might be yes, but teaching and learning are something that should always be improved since times and what students need to learn are changing by the day.

The needed skills in today's career world are so much different from what was needed 10 or 20 years ago. Emphasis is now on cooperation skills,

collaboration skills, etc. and Finland is not an exception in this. One of the latest teaching methods in mathematics which was focused on during this research is flipped learning. After careful consideration of other classroom teaching methods, the writer concluded that flipped learning is the best method that supports the idea of formative and supportive oral assessment. (Toviola, 2016). But even this classroom learning method has its worries and these were listed in Toviola and Silfverberg (2016).

One thing is sure since this classroom learning method is relatively new, more research will reveal how to deal with such worries and how to help improve oral formative assessment. Next, our attention will be turned to how the research was conducted what questions were asked, and what the writer hopes to find out at the end of the research.

2. Research Questions and Hypothesis

The writer believes that oral feedback by the teacher and oral expression of mathematics and science are highly undervalued in mathematics and science education, which when used to the maximum can improve the result of learning. Additionally, oral assessment as a formative and summative tool is under-exploited. The writer believes that there should be avenues for both students and teachers to have effective oral interaction as it offers the flexibility in articulation that the written form cannot offer.

Therefore, the research presented in this report broadly focuses on the qualitative effect of oral expression of mathematics in learning mathematics with emphasis on oral formative assessment. The report tries to answer the following:

- 1) Why oral assessment is important or needed?
- 2) Does oral assessment support the idea of individual learning?
- 3) What is students' opinion of oral assessment as a summative practice?
- 4) The effect of oral expression in the transfer of classroom knowledge to real life.
- 5) How to use the result to improve the teaching of mathematics?

The study hypothesizes that students who receive effective oral supportive feedback in mathematics from the teacher and who can articulate mathematical and scientific concepts clearly would have:

- 1) Greater understanding of the concept and better ability to connect the concept to real-life situations.
- 2) Fewer misconceptions about the concept.
- 3) Higher interest in the topic and greater motivation to pursue further studies in the topic.
- 4) Develop qualities such as cooperation and collaboration to work in their various careers.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Participants

Three Higher Secondary Schools (Lukio) were chosen for this research. There were no criteria for choosing them other than the fact that they are easily accessible and the writer has access to the mathematics teacher of the school. Also, since this was part of the Teacher as a Research course from the University of Helsinki which was included in the STEP, the basic practice and advanced practice present an opportunity for the research in terms of trying out teaching ideas.

Also, students of the schools were asked questions that were prepared by the writer but not in the form of a questionnaire about their opinion on the issue of oral assessment as a means of formative and summative assessment. Both the teachers and students want anonymity and that has been preserved greatly in this research. Since this research is qualitative, the results obtained were viewpoints and opinions rather than numerical facts and figures, and as such there was no need for tables and statistically generated charts.

3.2 Challenges

Several challenges were faced during this research exactly as mentioned in the earlier section. These practical difficulties are part of the everyday life of a teacher and show how the role of a teacher as a researcher, although fine in theory, is not necessarily so in practice. Two of these difficulties are described below:

- 1) **Strict IB schedule with reporting on class activities:** The IB program has a strict curriculum with exact time allocation for each topic. Moreover, it demands the reporting of class activities. The research of a teacher trainee during class hours cannot be accounted for as a normal class time and as such there is not much time to try out ideas outside the normal curriculum since students are only interested in what is in the curriculum which contributes towards the examination.

- 2) **Tight spring schedule:** The school had a tight spring schedule with many class hours taken away by holidays. This left barely enough time to cover every topic in mathematics, let alone conduct research. On the writer's part, the STEP's busy schedule also means that little time is left for the research.

Due to these two challenges, most of the research questions and ideas had to be adjusted to fit into a one-hour discussion with each of the three participating teachers and one 75-minute lesson session for each of the participating students. All participants were very cooperative and gave the best of their opinions during this research which the writer appreciates.

3.3 Questions Used

Below is the list of the questions which were used to discuss the opinion of the teacher and the students during the research:

- 1) How difficult do you think it is to use oral assessment in assessing student's skills and knowledge levels in mathematics?
- 2) How open are you as a teacher to use oral assessment as a summative assessment in mathematics?
- 3) How often do you use oral assessment whether as a means of formative or summative assessment?
- 4) What are the factors you think can be a limitation to oral assessment in mathematics?
- 5) How do you think these factors can be eliminated?
- 6) Provide at least 3 questions from any topic in mathematics taught at high school that you think is suitable for oral assessment.
- 7) How do you think your student would feel about oral assessment in mathematics?
- 8) Would you be interested in using this kind of assessment tool in class?

- 9) Do you prefer oral assessment over written assessment as a means of summative assessment?
- 10) How often do you think a teacher should give oral formative assessment to a student?
- 11) How do you feel when a teacher tells you that you need to improve on your studies?
- 12) What is your description of a good teacher?

During the research, there were other questions that arose because of the discussion which the writer has not prepared but which helped to better understand how students and teachers feel about oral assessment in terms of formative and summative.

4. Results Obtained

Since this research focuses on finding the importance of oral assessment in mathematics using a qualitative approach, most of the results that will be given are conclusions and inferences made by the writer with the help of the participants of the research. They are itemized as follows:

- 1) Oral Formative and supportive feedback helps to support motivation among students. This helps to answer the question of why oral assessment is important and why more teachers should consider including this as part of their practice as a teacher. It also means that students are ready to work more and are internally motivated which provides the best form of motivation.
- 2) Students are scared about how an error can cause lower scores in written assessments but feel that these can be eliminated in oral assessments. This was an opinion voiced by students who are in favor of oral summative assessment rather than written summative assessment. It now depends on a teacher who wants to use oral summative assessment to determine how to grade the discussion and correct the misconceptions of the students. This can also be a way to help students know what is their knowledge level.
- 3) Students think that it is not important to memorize formulas and as such they will appreciate questions that teach them how to apply a concept than how to solve a mathematical problem with such concepts. All the student participants echoed this opinion, but the writer thinks even though the main aim of mathematics and mathematics education is to be able to apply mathematical concepts to real-life situations, it is important to solve mathematical problems to gain mastery over the concepts. The writer also suggests to the teacher that rather than asking all questions about solving mathematics, it is important that teachers ask questions that help students to think logically and creatively, by doing this, students develop very high cognitive thinking

and skills. This will also make sure that the transfer of knowledge from the classroom to real life takes place.

- 4) Though most students still prefer written examinations, the prospect of having an oral summative assessment examination is interesting to them. This justifies the hypothesis that oral assessments can provide further options as a means of assessment.
- 5) Most teachers do not have any schedule of personal time with individual students as a form of supportive feedback. They only talk to students when things aren't going well. This presents a challenge and was one of the problems identified by this research. The teacher feels that good students do not need formative and supportive feedback since they are doing very well, but this research shows that even students with higher grades appreciate the feedback they get which serves as a source of motivation.
- 6) Most students agreed that using flipped learning in the class has helped them to learn individually and has helped them to become better at their own pace. This answers the question of whether oral formative assessment in mathematics can support the idea of individual learning. The writer believes since classroom teaching methods are changing, it is important that assessment styles also change.

5. Conclusion

This research has shown that oral formative and supportive feedback is sparingly used among mathematics teachers in the 3 schools where this research was conducted and it is safe to assume this might be the case in most of the schools in Finland concerning mathematics. Also, due to the new interest in oral assessment in mathematics, there was not so much knowledge about implementation and monitoring on the part of the teachers. It is recommended that further studies should allocate sufficient time for the interviews and the teacher must engage in one-on-one feedback sessions.

Nevertheless, the research suggests that students wish to have more oral formative feedback from the teacher to clarify their misconceptions help improve their understanding of the topic, and support their motivation for studying. Moreover, they wish to have oral assessment introduced as a summative practice, where they are graded on their ability to understand, apply, and articulate mathematical concepts.

Appendix I: Solution to the Problem of Over-grading and Under-grading

Source: Dunning et al. (2003).

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